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Inspection Reports in Turkey and United Kingdom: A Comparative Study of Inspections

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Abstract

This study aims to compare the school inspection reports prepared by educational inspectors in Turkey and the United Kingdom. In Turkey, educational inspection is carried out by the Educational Inspectors of the Ministry of National Education. On the other hand, educational inspection in the UK is carried out by Ofsted education inspectors. In both countries, it is compulsory to prepare an inspection report at the conclusion of an inspection, which sheds light on and evaluates the activities carried out at the school. The inspection reports are the subject of this study in terms of both form and content. The qualitative research method was used in the study and a document analysis was carried out. In this context, 10 inspection reports from both Turkey and the United Kingdom each were subjected to the inspection report review. A code was assigned to each inspection report. The reports originating from Turkey that were subjected to review were assigned the code TR, while the reports originating from the United Kingdom that were subjected to review were assigned the code UK. Titles of the inspection reports were determined and sample expressions related to each title were included in the text. As a result, although there are some similarities in the form of inspections, Ofsted reports were judged to be different, especially in terms of participation, evaluation of direct training activities, transparency and participation.

Keywords: School Inspection, Inspection Reports, Turkey, The United Kingdom, Ofsted

1. Introduction

One of the most important elements of the management process is inspections. During the early periods when management was first becoming accepted as a science, the inspection process was used as a control mechanism. However, in the following process, inspection ceased to be a control tool and became instead a feedback and correction tool.

As inspection are activities carried out on behalf of an authority, they constitute a very powerful and effective process. Therefore, inspection is an activity that is taken into consideration often by sub-administrative authorities. An inspection also sheds light on the nature and legality of the works that are being carried out within an

organization. Because every authority wants to know what is happening in the institutions they establish. And inspections are the most effective method for ensuring this. Thanks to the inspectors, it becomes possible to discover the activities that are being carried out within an organization. If these activities are below the desired level, then organization development processes are implemented. If officials are deemed to have a fault during this process, then legal investigation processes are initiated.

In the context of educational activities, measuring the quality of the works that are being carried out, providing feedback to employees about their work, and improving schools are matters of extreme significance. Education is a constantly changing and developing process. Moreover, education is also a social service that is affected and must be affected by external changes. Therefore, there is a need for a mechanism that will continuously monitor and develop educational organizations and provide data to the relevant authority. The name of this mechanism is inspection. It is not possible to talk about an educational activity that is uninspected.

Almost everywhere in the world, schools are being subjected to inspections. However, these inspection activities are carried out by using very different instruments. In some countries, there are inspectors responsible for the inspection of schools, and these inspectors inspect school administrators and teachers on behalf of the authority. The United Kingdom and Turkey are countries where this practice is being applied. In some countries, however, school inspections are carried out by parents. Finland can be given as an example of this model. Additionally, educational inspections are carried out by parent-teacher associations in certain countries, while independent inspectors fulfil this function in others. It is possible to give numerous examples regarding educational inspection models.

In the UK and Turkey, educational inspection activities are performed by educational inspectors. There is a public authority to which education inspectors are affiliated, and each educational activity that is being carried out in a school is documented in a report. Due to these similarities, inspection reports originating from Turkey and the United Kingdom were taken as the subject of this study.

2. Educational Inspection

Organizations are established to serve a common purpose and they must include a proper management system to achieve this goal (Topal & Atay, 2015). An effective model of inspection is a necessity for a good management system. In this context, the primary goal of the inspection is to determine to what level the organizational objectives are achieved and to take the necessary measures to improve the activities of the organization (Oynar, 2014). When considered in line with this purpose, it becomes clear that it is a necessity to inspect organizations (Kocer, 2015). Certain principles should be adhered to for the successful performance of the inspections, which are important for the efficiency of the organizations. Başar (2000) expressed the principles that should be considered during an inspection as purposefulness, planning, continuity, objectivity, integrity, contingency, openness and democracy.

Inspection of educational institutions is a duty that is rendered indispensable by the Constitution, laws and regulations. Educational inspection is a systematic and planned process aimed at ensuring the development of teachers and administrators in their profession, which in turn enables the development of education and teaching (Aldemir, 2012). Since inspection evaluates an organization as a whole and enables the correction and improvement of goals according to the results of this evaluation, it contributes to the realization of the objectives of education systems. It is possible to say that the development, effectiveness and problem-solving skills of organizations that do not take action based on inspection results are left to chance. The extent to which educational institutions achieve their objectives is monitored through inspections. Necessary measures are also taken in cases where these objectives are not achieved. Due to these features, inspections have an indispensable value and function in education and school systems (Gokce, 2009). It is necessary to adhere to certain principles to achieve the objectives of the inspection process, which is important for ensuring the efficient execution of education (Kocer, 2015). These principles are explained in the By-Laws of the Inspection Board of the Ministry of National Education as follows (MEB, 2017):

- Individual, organizational and environmental differences must be taken into account.

- Guiding and preventive supervision should be brought to the fore.
- Inspection activities should aim to correct, improve and develop.
- It should be ensured that good examples encountered during inspections are disseminated.
- Possible risks in the education and management systems should be eliminated.
- Irregularities and corruption within the system must be eliminated.
- Inspections should be open, transparent, equal, democratic, participatory, holistic, reliable and impartial.
- Cooperation is essential in inspections.
- Successes should be highlighted.
- Inspections are scientific and objective.
- Effectiveness, economy and efficiency should be the core principles of inspection activities.

The professional development of teachers, which is deemed to be one of the most important factors in increasing the quality in educational organizations, is a very important issue. Therefore, one of the priorities of educational inspections should be the training and development of teachers (Okutan, 1996). It is possible to define inspection as a multifaceted process that focuses on instruction and provides teachers with information about their teaching so as to develop instructional skills to improve performance (Wanzare & da Costa, 2000). Also, the belief that teachers are not fully prepared when they start their duties and that their self-improvement is a desirable assumption proves the need for inspection (Chidobi, 2015).

2.1 Educational Inspection in Turkey

In terms of history, inspection systems in educational organizations hold a long-established trove of knowledge (Ilgan, 2018). Changes and developments in the inspection system first started to take shape with the establishment of an inspection infrastructure in the Tanzimat Period of the Ottoman Empire, during which innovations and transformations were taking place in all aspects of both the society and the state (Buluc, 1997). There are historical documents showing that the units responsible for the inspection of Sibyaniye (primary school) and Rustiye (secondary school) schools were established in 1846 (Usta, 2017). Schools in the Ottoman period were generally modern schools inspired by the Western style, and these schools were run by religious units. These schools did not have a regular inspection system or a board, except for the Sibyan and Rustiye Schools. However, after 1862, the concepts of inspection and inspectors began to appear in the Ottoman education system. In this period, inspectors were called "muin" and "muhakkik." In a general sense, the word "muin" meant "inspector" during that period and it describes a person who provides consultation, examination, direction or incentive. Regulations and changes regarding inspections in the Ottoman period can be explained in a historical order as follows (Usta, 2017):

- The main purpose of the inspections carried out in 1838 was to determine the deficiencies of the schools and also to attempt to reduce or remedy them. However, more tangible steps were taken regarding the inspection systems in the Ottoman Empire only during the Tanzimat Period, which started in 1839.
- In 1862, Sibyan and Rustiye schools were inspected for the first time in their history.
- In 1875, it became compulsory for schools to keep a book for inspections.
- In 1876, legal inspection directives were published.
- In 1910/1911, the directive regarding the duties of primary education inspectors was published.
- With the regulations published in 1911, the concepts of management and inspection were distinguished from each other.
- In 1912, the duties of the inspectors were stated explicitly.
- In 1913, it was decided that primary education inspections would be made by primary education inspectors and the duties of inspectors were determined as inspection, investigation and informing the public.
- With the directive published in 1914, the responsibilities of the inspectors and the methods they implement in executing these responsibilities were determined.

As explained above, the inspection activities in the Ottoman Empire were established through constant change and development. Many sources do not go farther back than 1918 in describing the chronology of this process. However, looking at the developments written above regarding educational inspection in the Ottoman period, it becomes clear that many documents describing the duties of primary school inspectors can be encountered (Ozmen, Acikses, Usta & Uluerler, 2014).

If this situation is examined in the context of our more recent history, it can be seen that "educational inspectors" were responsible for the inspection of primary education teachers and "Ministry Inspectors," who were assigned by the central government, were responsible for the supervision of secondary education teachers until the amendments introduced by the "Decree-Law No. 652 on the Organization and Duties of the Ministry of National Education" that entered into force in 2011. With this decree, Ministry inspectors were renamed as "National Education Inspectors" and education inspectors were renamed as "Provincial Education Inspectors," and the areas of responsibility for these officials were distinguished from each other. With these regulations, the supervision and inspection of all formal and non-formal education institutions and provincial and district national education directorates were assigned to provincial education inspectors. Thus, the mandate of provincial education inspectors was expanded. While the positive and negative aspects of this restructuring have not yet been fully explored, it was decided in 2014 that the titles of "MNE Supervisor" and "Provincial Education Supervisor" will be combined under the term "Education Supervisor." It has been stated that these inspectors, called the "Education Inspectors," will take part in in-service training activities related to the training of education administrators, research and development studies, and institutional inspections. However, it has been stated that the in-class inspections of teachers will be carried out by school principals instead of inspectors (Cicek Saglam & Aydogmus, 2017).

In line with the amendments made with the Regulation on the Inspection Board of the Ministry of National Education published in 2017, the Directorate of the Inspection Board was re-attached to the Minister. With this regulation, the establishment or closure of provincial study centres to inspect and supervise the services provided by the Ministry within the scope of educational inspection was permitted, provided that they are deemed necessary (MEB, 2017). Inspectors employed in the fields of supervision, on-the-job training, inspection, evaluation, examination, research and investigation can express their opinions through the "Examination and Research Report" (Okutan, 1996).

2.2 Educational Inspection Reports in Turkey

Article 56 of the Fundamental Law of National Education Numbered 1739 states "the Ministry of National Education is responsible for the execution, supervision and inspection of education and training services provided on behalf of the State per the provisions of this law." Education inspectors perform this task on behalf of the Ministry of Education (Sagir, 2018). In addition to their powers granted to them by the legislation, the inspectors also have certain responsibilities. One of these responsibilities is writing inspection reports in line with the inspection principles and reporting standards and submitting these to the relevant units and persons (Akin, 2015). The inspection report is the document that includes the identifications made by the inspectors during the performance of their duty. "An inspection report is a report that is prepared as a result of the inspection of works and processes that are carried out by the establishments, institutions or personnel that are subject to the inspection of the Ministry and the organizations of the Ministry, and these reports are prepared per the type of inspection and in line with the inspection principles and reporting standards." (MEB, 2021).

The reporting principles that inspectors must comply with can be listed as follows: (MEB, 2016):

- *"The purpose, scope, findings, problematic areas, recommendations and results of the supervision and inspection should be stated in the report.*
- *The statements in these reports should be accurate, impartial, constructive, clear and understandable.*
- *The findings and suggestions that were included in previous reports should also be included.*
- *Reports should be completed within the specified period and submitted to the relevant authority.*

- *If there are matters regarding certain needs related to the requirements of the work that should be reported immediately, an interim report may be filed until a full report can be prepared.*
- *Documents that served as the basis for the report can be annexed to the report.*
- *Good examples of practices identified during inspection activities should be included in the report.*
- *The principle of confidentiality should be observed in the preparation, presentation and storage of reports.*
- *A section explaining the findings, suggestions, opinions and remarks based on evidence and legislation should be included in reports following a summary of the current situation.*
- *Grammar and spelling rules should be observed in the preparation of reports."*

After the conclusion of an inspection, a sufficient number of copies of the report that was prepared in accordance with the aforementioned guidelines should be submitted, alongside its annexes, if any, by the educational inspector to the Directorate for Guidance and Inspection as soon as possible.

2.3 Educational Inspection in the UK

Like in many other areas, the United Kingdom is a prominent country in the field of education. The education system of the United Kingdom, which houses many of the high ranking universities in the world, such as Oxford and Cambridge, is not only very successful in the area of higher education, but also other levels of education. To achieve this remarkable success, many reforms have been carried out in the United Kingdom, especially after the 1980s, and these reforms allowed the education system of the country to reach an important point (Gonulacar, 2018). Undoubtedly, the inspection mechanisms played an important role in the British education system reaching this point.

Educational activities in the UK are conducted locally. Educational activities are under the responsibility of the "Local Education Authority (LEA)." This institution is authorized in all matters related to quality, cost, responsibilities, personnel needs and training regarding education for all educational levels, except for universities. The central system determines the general framework such as goals, objectives and standards. The implementation of this general framework in local governments is carried out by the local inspection board (Gonulacar, 2018, 25).

The foundations of Ofsted were laid with the Education Act, which was implemented in 1992. Ofsted, which is the abbreviation of The Office for Standards in Education (Guzel, Arslan, Aktekin, 2020), is the top educational inspection authority in the United Kingdom. Ofsted is an organization that inspects educational activities. Ofsted's mission is to "make sure that organisations providing education, training and care services in England do so to a high standard " (OFSTED, 2021). Ofsted is headed by a government-funded and queen-appointed chief inspector (Matthews and Sammons, 2004). Ofsted inspectors are trained directly by the institution and supervised by Her Majesty's chief inspector. To become an Ofsted inspector, it is necessary to have expertise in the field of education and five years of experience as a director of an educational institution (Guzel, Arslan & Aktekin, 2020). Ofsted, whose recruitment process takes 5 to 12 months on average, aims to operate as an independent and impartial institution (OFSTED, 2021).

In essence, Ofsted applies a type of performance evaluation to institutions that are under its jurisdiction. The quality of the education of the schools, the level of achievement of the students, the psychological, moral and social development levels of the students, and whether the financial resources of the schools are used correctly are inspected by this organization (Ozcan, 2011). Ofsted plays a major role in the education system of the United Kingdom and it holds a remarkable amount of influence on students, teachers and educational institutions. It contributes to the achievement of the aims of the British education system by closely monitoring the quality and functionality of education in educational institutions (Chapman, 2002, 257).

2.4 Educational Inspection Reports in the UK

According to Ofsted, schools should be inspected regularly every 4 years. During this period, schools conduct their own inspections once a year. Ofsted inspectors evaluate schools with an evaluation form that includes the ratings of "Outstanding, Good, Requires Improvement and Inadequate." Measures are taken to remedy the areas that were deemed inadequate during the evaluation process. Schools that fail to demonstrate progress and change despite these measures are closed. After each evaluation, feedback is provided to the institution and parents (Gonulacar, 2018). The characteristics of a school that has received an "Outstanding" rating are described as follows: "A very good rated school is a school that meets the needs of all students and achieves effective results. These schools have the equipment for providing students with education and training that is necessary for the employment that comes after education." The characteristics of a school that has received a "Good" rating are described as follows: "This school is also an effective school that meets the needs of students. This school can prepare students effectively for the next stage of their education or employment. A school that has received a "Requires Improvement" rating is described as follows: "A school that requires improvement is not inadequate, but neither is it satisfactory. The schools which are rated as requiring improvement will receive another inspection within 24 months." A school that has received an "Inadequate" rating is described as follows: This school has significant weaknesses and is generally inadequate. Significant improvements are required in this school. The management and leadership, however, are judged to be Grade 3 or above. This school will be inspected regularly by Ofsted inspectors. This is a school that requires special measures and it is unable to provide its students with an acceptable standard of education. Additionally, the school's leaders, administrators or managers do not have the capacity to achieve the necessary improvements. This school will be inspected regularly by Ofsted inspectors."

In the education system of the UK, parents can choose a school for their children and are able to send their children to any school that they desire. Parents also take into account OFSTED reports when searching for suitable schools for their children. The quality of the school, its financial resources and how it uses these resources, to what extent it achieves the educational objectives specified in the education law are clearly stated in OFSTED reports. In this context, OFSTED reports are an important factor in providing the necessary information to parents and pushing schools to make the necessary changes and innovations (OFSTED, 2021). Again, for OFSTED, inspection reports are seen as a part of the inspection, not a result. (Field, Greensteet, Kusel & Parsons, 1996).

Ofsted's institutional inspections take 2 days and the number of inspectors to take part in the inspection varies according to the size of the school and the number of students and staff. There are three different types of inspections: Full time, short time and monitoring inspections. Full-time inspections take 2 days, and they are reserved for institutions that have just started operating or have received inadequate ratings in the previous inspection. As opposed to full-time inspections, short-time inspections are short-term visits to institutions that have received good and passing ratings in previous inspections. Monitoring inspections, on the other hand, are short-term visits to institutions that have previously received inadequate ratings and will be subjected to full-time inspections. These are conducted before full-time inspections to monitor the activities of the institution (Güzel, Arslan & Aktekin, 2020, 18). "Outstanding schools" are schools that passed the inspection with full marks, and thus, they are not subjected to routine inspections. In the next inspection, they are inspected via a short-term inspection. Good schools, like very good schools, are subject to short-term inspections. These inspections are done in order to determine whether their quality of education is persistent. Schools rated as requiring improvement are those that are at a level that can continue their educational activities but need to be re-inspected within 24 months after the inspection. Inadequate schools, on the other hand, are schools that are either subject to special measures or completely closed due to their inadequacies (Buyruk, 2018). These inspection types are determined according to previous inspection processes and to the overall ratings of the schools.

It is not mandatory to inform the institution prior to the inspection. However, they are usually informed. Particular attention is paid to gathering opinions from parents about the institution, as well as collecting complaints and requests. Lessons are observed during the observation process. Interviews are also held with parents, staff, teachers and students. Schools are generally inspected under the headings of quality of education, behaviour and attitudes, personal development, and management and leadership (Güzel, Arslan & Aktekin, 2020).

Chief Inspector holds the primary responsibility during the inspection process. After the inspection, a draft report is prepared and sent to the school administration in advance in order to prevent possible objections. The opinions of the school administration are taken. As a result of these processes, the final report is shared simultaneously on the institution and the Ofsted websites within 25 days (OFSTED, 2021). Inspection results are followed by the institution, parents and local media. Interest is shown to schools that are rated good or that has shown improvements. It is the responsibility of the school to make the necessary arrangements in line with the report (Rosenthal, 2004, 145). The following figure shows the ratings certain schools received as a result of the Ofsted inspections in 2017 (NAO, 2021).

Ofsted had graded two-thirds of schools as good at August 2017

Figure 1: Ofsted's grades for the overall effectiveness of state-funded schools in August 2017

Source: <https://www.nao.org.uk/>

The figure above demonstrates that Ofsted inspectors inspect a total of 21,544 schools in a year and that 1,386 of these schools are special education schools and kindergartens, 3,375 are secondary and high schools, and 16,873 are primary schools. 4,229 of these schools received an "inadequate" rating. This corresponds to 20% of the total number.

OFSTED is a highly influential institution in the British education system. The effectiveness or inadequacy of schools is determined by OFSTED. Ofsted reports constitute an important point of reference for parents' choice of school. Whether a school is good or bad is determined by the report filed by Ofsted (Guzel, Arslan & Aktekin, 2020, 18). For the public of the United Kingdom, Ofsted is an important and reliable resource. According to a study conducted in this context, Ofsted reports have approximately a 50% effect on the parents' decisions regarding the selection of schools (NAO, 2021). Thanks to the elements involved in the inspection process, the transparent sharing of results, and the strict enforcement of the inspection results, Ofsted is recognized as successful in inspecting the schools in the United Kingdom.

2.5 Inspection and Regulation Principles According to OFSTED

Ofsted takes the following principles as the basis while carrying out educational inspections (OFSTED, 2021):

- Inspections should be done in a way that encourages services to be user-oriented, to develop institutions, and to use their resources effectively and efficiently.
- Inspections are independent. With a perspective that examines the institution externally, it provides a review that describes what needs to be done in order to achieve developments and improvements.
- Inspections provide information to families, caregivers, learners and employers on the quality of education and care. These are allowed to make sound decisions as a result of published inspection reports.
- Inspections provide assurances to the public and the government as to whether education, skills and childcare standards are met, whether the public budget is well spent and whether safety regulations are effective.

It is important to have a communication environment between the Inspectors and service providers that is based on professionalism and courtesy in the attempt to apply these principles. Inspectors apply the highest standards in the performance of their work. Inspectors are expected to approach each individual they encounter during the inspection in a fair, respectful and sensitive manner. To meet these expectations, inspectors will:

- Carry out their evaluations objectively. Act impartially.
- Always follow and respect Ofsted's values.
- Carry out their evaluations according to the general framework and national standards.
- Base their inspections on clear and strong evidence.
- Communicate purposefully and productively with those who are being inspected and provide them with information about their evaluations in a precise but clear manner.
- Pay utmost attention to the confidentiality of information regarding their work.
- Use their titles only in their works and relationships related to Ofsted.
- School and institution administrators, teachers and staff also have certain responsibilities. These are:
 - They will communicate with the inspectors with respect and courtesy and behave professionally.
 - They must openly and honestly allow inspectors to carry out the inspection.
 - They will ensure that inspectors are able to gather and access evidence. This includes interviews with the students.
 - They will act together to reduce confusion, stress and bureaucratic issues.

Inspectors judge the state of the institution they are inspecting after gathering sufficient evidence regarding the school. While making this assessment, they also consider the quality of education, behaviour and attitudes, personal development, leadership and management areas (OFSTED, 2021). In general, it is possible to say that Ofsted reports are written from a holistic perspective.

3. Method

In this section of the study, the research method, how data is collected, findings and results are described.

3.1 The Research Method

The qualitative research method was used in this study. The qualitative research method is accepted to be a type of research in which approaches such as observations, interviews and document analyses are used and a process is followed to reveal the events in a realistic and holistic manner in their natural environment (Yildirim & Simsek,

2008). It is possible to use different models within the scope of qualitative research. One of these is document review or document analysis.

Document analysis is a systematic procedure used for examining or evaluating documents. Like other analytical methods in qualitative research, document analysis requires the analysis of data. The researcher then interprets the results to extrapolate meanings, gain insight and develop empirical works. There are a variety of documents that can be used for systematic evaluation as a part of a study. These can include organizational agendas, meeting minutes, guides, books, journals, diaries and event programs, letters, maps, radio and television programs, and organizational reports. Such documents can be found in libraries, newspaper archives, historical sources or institutional archives. Researchers usually review previous literature and examine reports in detail as part of their studies (Bowen, 2009, 27-28). Usually, the documents or data obtained by the researcher at the beginning are raw. The researcher systematizes this information with an appropriate method. She categorizes, interprets and discusses this information. Thus, she creates a scientific study.

3.2 Data Collection

Inspection reports were used as data within the scope of this study. These inspection reports constitute the only type of data within this study. The study aims to reach a conclusion by comparing the reports reflecting the two countries. The reports for the UK were obtained from the OFSTED website. The inspection reports of Turkey has been provided by the researchers themselves. Attention has been paid to ensure that the reports obtained from these countries represent the countries geographically. A total of 20 inspection reports have been examined, with 10 (kindergarten + primary education + secondary education) for each country. The school inspection reports of Turkey were coded and numbered as TR and school reports of the United Kingdom were coded and numbered as UK.

3.3 Data Regarding The Reports Obtained under The Research

The inspection reports were classified according to the type of the school; whether kindergartens, primary schools or secondary schools. The characteristics of the reports obtained in the scope of the research are given in the table below:

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of The Reports That are The Subjects of The Study

	Kindergarten	Primary Education (Elementary and secondary schools)	Secondary Education	City Centre/ Rural	Level of Achievement	Number of the pages of the report	Date
TR1	✓			Rural	X	10	2019
TR2	✓			City Centre	X	11	2019
TR3		✓		City Centre	X	14	2020
TR4		✓		City Centre	X	10	2019
TR5		✓		City Centre	X	10	2019
TR6		✓		City Centre	X	9	2019
TR7		✓		Rural	X	9	2019

TR8		✓	Rural	X	15	2019
TR9		✓	City Centre	X	14	2019
TR10		✓	Rural	X	13	2020
UK1	✓		City Centre	Requires Improvement	13	2017
UK2	✓		Rural	Good	10	2016
UK3		✓ Mixed	City Centre	Outstanding	10	2013
UK4		✓ Mixed	City Centre	Outstanding	10	2015
UK5		✓	City Centre	Requires Improvement	11	2018
UK6		✓ Mixed	Rural	Good	9	2014
UK7		✓ Mixed	City Centre	Good	8	2016
UK8		✓ Mixed	Rural	Good	13	2018
UK9		✓ Mixed	Rural	Inadequate	13	2019
UK10		✓ Mixed	Rural	Good	9	2013

Examination of Table 1 reveals that 4 of the analyzed reports were on kindergartens, 12 were in primary school and secondary school (or primary schools) and 4 were on secondary education schools. Schools indicated as "mixed" in the Table provide mixed education in terms of gender. 9 of the schools are in rural areas (village, town or county), while 11 of them are in the city centres. There are no indications within these reports that demonstrate the level of achievement of the schools in Turkey. Therefore, this situation was indicated with the X symbol. Regarding the level of achievement presented by the schools in the United Kingdom, 2 schools were rated with "Requires Improvement," 5 were rated with "Good," 2 were rated with "Outstanding" and 1 was rated with "Inadequate." The number of pages of the analysed inspection reports is between 8 and 15 pages. The oldest report is dated 2013, and the newest is dated 2020.

While analysing the reports, the headings in the reports were taken as criteria. The headings included within the reports were provided in Table 2.

Table 2: Sections of The Inspection Reports

Sections of the Inspection Reports (TR)	Sections of the Inspection Reports (UK)
Cover	Overall effectiveness
Introduction	Summary of key findings for parents and pupils
Education and Training Environments	Information about this inspection
Safety Precautions	Inspection judgements
Education and Training Activities	a) The leadership and management.
Management Activities	b) The behaviour and safety of pupils.
Financial Affairs and Transactions	c) The quality of teaching.
Movable Goods Transactions	d) The achievement of pupils.

Exemplary Applications in the Institution General Evaluation	e) The early years' provision School details Concerns and complaints about Ofsted
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When Table 2 is examined it is seen that there are 10 main headings in the TR coded reports. There are 6 main headings in the UK coded reports. There are secondary headings under the main headings in both reports.

3.4 Analysis of the Inspection Reports from Turkey

The inspection reports of the schools in Turkey can be accessed from open environments, such as the website of the related school or the TIB (Turkish Inspection Board). In addition, it is also possible to access detailed documents on how inspections are to be conducted on the TIB website. The guidelines and legal texts on this site that determine the framework and legal basis of the inspection reports are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Turkey Inspection Board Web site

Source: <http://tkb.meb.gov.tr/www/yayinlarimiz/icerik/13>

The following headings are included in the inspection reports, respectively:

Cover form: This section includes introductory information about the school, such as the e-mail and phone number of the school, the date of the previous inspection, the number of teachers and students (TR1, TR2, TR3, TR4, TR5, TR6, TR7, TR8, TR9, TR10).

Introduction: In the introduction of the inspection report, a brief summary is provided about the legal basis of this inspection and the way the inspection is carried out. An example introductory statement is provided below (TR1):

“According to the Ministry's Office Approval dated 2.12.2018 and numbered E..... and the appointment orders of the Inspection Board dated 8.06.2019 and numbered E....., the inspection of the kindergarten named, which is located at the district of the province, has been carried out by our group between the dates of 08-11.10.2019. The processes and results related to the Education and Training Environments,

Educational Activities, Management Activities and Financial Affairs and Operations were examined and evaluated using the precision sampling method in cooperation with the relevant individuals and units and in accordance with the legislation and the predetermined objectives and goals. The issued determined in this regard were explained below."

Education and Training Environments: How many buildings and classrooms the school consists of and the condition of spaces such as gardens, libraries and laboratories is included under this heading. An example statement about education and training environments is given below (TR2):

"It was observed that the school started providing education in the academic year of 2007-2008 and that the school building consists of a single block and a single floor. It was seen that the Turkish flag was hoisted and the Atatürk corner was arranged. School sections were noted to be adequate, suitable for service, tidy and clean and the school garden is arranged in a manner that will allow children to walk around and play. The garden is afforested, there are playgrounds for children to play and the necessary precautions are taken for the physically disabled. Educational environments are arranged in accordance with the developmental characteristics of children, and the entrance and waiting areas are arranged properly."

Security precautions: Under this heading, there are determinations as to whether a report was received on the earthquake resistance of the building or not, whether the fire detection system of the building is operational or not, and whether the electrical installation of the building is inspected regularly or not. An example statement on this issue is given below (TR3):

"It was observed that alarm and personnel evacuation drills regarding earthquakes and fires have been carried in the institution, that reports regarding these drills have been prepared, and that the first-aid cabinet includes all tools and materials that it is required to contain. It has been determined that the layout and order of the boiler room are proper, the boiler has a maintenance certificate, an instruction manual is posted in an appropriate part of the boiler room, and 12 of the 14 security cameras in the institution are in working condition. The institution is constantly monitored with a camera system, and the first-aid cabinet includes all tools and materials that it is required to contain."

Education and Training Activities: Guidance activities, whether the provided education is in accordance with the curriculum or not, the occupational development activities of the teachers and the characteristics of parent meetings are addressed under this heading. Students who require special education, the status of the students receiving inclusive education, whether the teachers conduct house visitations or not, the attendance of the students and the dropout status of the students and other matters are also discussed here. An example statement on this subject is given below (TR5):

"It was observed that unitized annual plans and lesson plans were made, the objectives and outcomes specified in the curriculum were taken as basis in measuring and evaluating the student's achievement, and the teaching methods and techniques to be applied in the teaching of the lessons were determined at the class teachers' board meeting held at the beginning of the academic year. It was noted that questions and answer keys were also prepared before the examinations and stored with exam papers, and an individualized education program was prepared for students receiving inclusive education. It was observed that activities were undertaken within the scope of individual and group counselling services, and the annual report regarding guidance and psychological counselling services was prepared."

Additionally, corrections are requested by checking the inspection reports in cases of negative situations related to education and training activities. An example statement regarding an identified negative situation is as follows (TR5):

"It was observed that post-examination analyses to determine whether learning deficits were remedied and predicted outputs were achieved are not being conducted after written examinations."

The solution proposed by the inspector who has inspected this matter, which is deemed to be problematic, is as follows (TR5):

"After each exam, both the course and the group teachers should conduct question and outcome correlation and analysis activities specific to each lesson in order to identify the areas where learning deficiencies exist and take the necessary measures to remedy this situation. This process must always be structured in a manner that will provide the students with the opportunity to learn."

Management Activities: The number of administrators working in the institution, the education received by the school staff, the status of the books and files that should be kept by the school, whether the teachers' board meetings are held or not, whether there is cooperation with other institutions related to the school or not, and the projects carried out at the school are matters addressed in this section. An example statement on this subject is as follows (TR7):

"It was observed that a strategic plan was prepared for the school, the vision and mission of the school were determined, analyses were carried out, the strategic plan monitoring and evaluation unit performed its works, the goals were mostly achieved, and the efforts for unattained goals were continued. It has been observed that the division of labour was made among the personnel and their duties were communicated to the personnel in return for signature. "It was observed that the teachers' board convened at the beginning, middle and end of the year in line with the agenda items announced to teachers 2 days before the meeting and decisions were taken during these meetings. It has been determined that ballot box and election boards have been established for the election of the school student council chairmanship (TR5). "It was understood that the professional studies were carried out within the framework of the program received from the Ministry, the school principal attended the lectures of the teachers for supervisory purposes, and the necessary follow-up and inspections regarding the works and procedures to be carried out electronically were performed (TR8)."

It was noted that the problems observed under this heading were expressed in the reports. An example problem is expressed in the following terms (TR8):

"It has been determined that the findings and suggestions of the school principal are generally included in the meeting minutes of the Teachers Board, and the opinions and thoughts of the teachers are not included."

The following expressions were proposed as a solution to this problem (TR8):

"The teachers' opinions and suggestions should be included in the meeting minutes of the Teachers Board in line with Article 109/6 of Secondary Education Institutions Regulation."

Financial Affairs and Transactions: Whether the Parent-Teacher Association has been established, whether there are any allowances in the bank account of this association, and whether these allowances were spent in accordance with their purposes are matters included under this heading. An example statement on this subject is as follows (TR8):

"It was observed that all income and expenses of the school and all donations in cash or in-kind were registered to the TEFBIS module (Turkish Education Financing and Educational Expenditures Information Management System) and activities within the scope of extracurricular education were carried out in accordance with the program prepared by 3

teachers. It was noted that deductions from salaries and wages are made in accordance with the legislation and an approved copy of the relevant documents are kept in the institution, that the income of the family association is spent in line with the primary needs of the school and students in line with the framework of the budget discipline, and that the board of directors of the association kept the minutes of the general assembly, as well as their decision books, income and expense books, incoming-outgoing documents books and expenditure documents."

Movable Goods Transactions: This heading addresses whether the tools and equipment of the school are recorded in the electronic registration system. An example statement on this subject is as follows (TR8):

"It was determined that the numbers of the durable movables were not permanently inscribed on the movables, that the list of movables that are used in classrooms, units and common areas were not up to date, that movable delivery documents were not issued for durable movables assigned for usage, and that insufficient care was placed into registering materials obtained from the parent school association's account to the movable property management system."

Exemplary Applications in the Institution: In this section, a record is kept as to whether there are any applications in the school that is being inspected that can serve as an example for other institutions. An example statement on this subject is as follows (TR4):

"It was observed that an atmosphere that is focused on learning has been established in the school, that the teachers work in harmony with the administrators to develop and improve the education process, that the entirety of the institution participates in a project that was produced within this context with the mindset of "All of Us Are One," and that unique works are being exhibited in the school environment that demonstrate historical events."

In the other 9 inspection reports reviewed, the statement *"There are no applications in the institution that can serve as an example to other institutions."* was used.

General evaluation: General opinions of the inspectors performing the inspection are provided under this section. The statements within this scope are the same in nearly all of the reports. Example statements on this subject are as follows (TR1, TR2, TR3, TR4, TR5, TR6, TR7, TR8, TR9, TR10):

"The inspection of the institution was carried out intermittently by our Inspectorate. The supervision and inspection activities were initiated by holding a preliminary meeting with the directors of the institution, and explanations were made regarding the supervision and inspection activities to be carried out. The activities carried out by our group were carried out in cooperation with the directors of the institution, teachers and staff. Our understanding of inspection prioritizes the guidance approach and it is based on the principles of democracy, planning, transparency and objectivity. It is vital to ensure an objective evaluation during an inspection. The activities of the institution were examined with the precision sampling method and completed as planned in the context of contributing to the efficiency and effectiveness of the education and management activities and financial works and transactions."

3.5 Analysis of the Inspection Reports from the United Kingdom

The inspection reports of schools in the United Kingdom are available in open environments, such as the school website or the Ofsted website. You can find the inspection reports on Ofsted's website via a search engine (under the title of "Find an inspection report"). In this search engine, it is possible to find classifications of schools or

institutions based on their education level (primary education, secondary education, other education levels). The search engine screen is shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3. Ofsted Website

Source: <https://reports.Ofsted.gov.uk/>

The following headings are included in the inspection reports, respectively:

Overall Effectiveness: This section contains the headings of "Effectiveness of leadership and management, quality of teaching, learning and assessment, personal development, behaviour and welfare, outcomes for pupils and judgments of the previous inspections." The ratings these headings received from the general inspection are specified in this section. There are four possible evaluation results. These are "Outstanding, Good, Requires Improvement, and Inadequate."

Summary of key findings for parents and pupils: This section starts with the score the school received from the inspection. For example (UK3): "This is an outstanding school." Following this explanation, information that may be useful for students and parents is provided. Below are some example statements (UK3).

"Students behave extremely well in the lessons and in the school environment. They feel very safe at school and enjoy a wide variety of activities planned for them. The curriculum is creative and well planned to enable students to develop literacy and numeracy skills and to provide excellent opportunities to support their spiritual, moral, social and cultural development."

Some statements about a school that received an "Inadequate" rating during an inspection are as follows (UK9):

"Students have very limited opportunities to improve their literacy skills. There are few opportunities for students to solve their numeracy problems. Leaders and directors have failed to impose a curriculum that promotes respect for all special groups that are protected by the 2010 Equality Act. Whereas the implementation of this law provides the students with the opportunity to improve their understanding skills."

Inspectors make some suggestions for schools that are rated "inadequate." Some examples of the expressions included in these recommendations are as follows (UK9):

"The entirety of the staff must have great expectations regarding what pupils, especially the most talented ones, can and must achieve. Teachers should provide students with

opportunities to practice their literacy skills, especially in English written work and other curricula. Opportunities should be provided for students in the first stage to improve their problem solving and reasoning skills in mathematics. Directors should broaden their skills towards transforming themselves into becoming effective leaders to ensure students' progress. Managers and directors must ensure that the curriculum is broad and balanced. This allows students to learn and progress in a wide variety of subjects. Learning plans that contain the knowledge, understanding and skills that students will learn and acquire should be developed. An effective evaluation system should be implemented so that leaders and teachers can accurately monitor students' progress in the curriculum."

Information about this inspection: In this section, a summary of the activities the inspectors performed before, during and after the inspection is given. Additionally, this section includes the in-class observations of the inspectors, the students they have listened to, the findings resulting from the examination of the textbooks of the students, interviews with the school directors and the views of the local administration regarding the school. Moreover, this section also includes information concerning interviews with parents, examined files, observations about students' behaviour and attitudes, and how many days the inspection took (UK6, UK9, UK10). The following is an example of the information contained in inspection reports regarding this subject (UK3):

"The inspectors observed 16 lessons fully or partially, seven of which were joint observations with members of the school leadership team. A number of student works were examined. A school commission was visited and some time was spent in a reading workshop for a group of parents. Meetings were held with the chairman of the parent-teacher association (Executive Board) and three other officers, the school principal, other school leaders and a representative from the local government. Inspectors spoke with two groups of students, in lectures and around the school, in an informal manner. An inspector also listened to some reading studies of certain students. The inspectors examined the school's records on monitoring and quality of education and training, the student standards, and improvements and procedures to ensure students' safety. Additionally, they also reviewed the records concerning the performance of the personnel, the judgments of the school regarding its own performance, the documents and policies regarding improvement plans. 62 responses were made to the online "Parents' Opinion" questionnaire. 18 questionnaires were filled out by the staff. All these opinions and observations were evaluated by the inspection team."

Inspection judgments: The following subheadings are addressed under this heading: a) Leadership and management. b) The behaviour and safety of pupils. c) The quality of teaching. d) The achievement of pupils; and e) The evaluation of the previous years. Each of these subheadings is rated and evaluated. The first rating is "Outstanding," the second rating is "Good," the third rating is "Requires Improvement," and the fourth rating is "Inadequate."

a) The leadership and management: In this section, the matters of whether the headmaster was able to establish a team that is highly motivated, whether he visits classrooms and provides feedback to teachers, whether student funds are spent effectively, the level of equal opportunities and opportunities at school, whether the students achieved any progress compared to the previous year; whether the building is being ensured and whether good relations with local authorities have been established are addressed. An example statement on this subject is as follows (UK4):

"The headmaster has assembled a highly motivated team that focuses fully on the success and welfare of the students. There is a consensus among the Staff that the school is well managed and directed. One of the staff members responding to the questionnaire commented, "I am proud to be working in a school where the children's love of learning, the pleasure they get from school, the safety of the students and the enjoyment they get from their friendships is high." The school's continuous endeavours and its pursuit of improvement are at the centre of the school's success."

b) The behaviour and safety of pupils: In this section, issues such as student behaviour, student welfare, students' relationships with each other, student participation, whether students are safe, possible threats to students, not being afraid of making mistakes are addressed. An example statement on this subject is as follows (UK6):

"The pupils are aware of the potential dangers surrounding them. They know that they should not go beyond the limits set by the adults who take care of them. Mutual respect between adults and students creates an environment where it is safe to make mistakes. When asked about the mistakes that the teacher stated in his work, a 1st-grade pupil replied confidently: 'It's okay to make mistakes, I've learned something new. My sense of responsibility has grown. The pupil carefully transferred the water from the indoor faucet to the garden area to water the seeds planted in the schoolyard.'"

c) The quality of teaching: Under this heading, the findings of the Inspectors obtained during the observation of the lessons are mentioned. The extent to which students are motivated to learn, the quality of teaching, how teachers evaluate students, the level of the students' mathematics and language skills, and whether or not there are activities such as revealing students' abilities are discussed under this heading. An example statement on this subject is as follows (UK10):

"Teaching has improved considerably and is generally at a better level than before. Indeed, inadequate teaching was not observed during the inspection, and many traits were better and they were, in some cases, changed spectacularly. Three joint lesson observations conducted with school leaders confirmed that the school's perspective of quality teaching was correct."

d) The achievement of pupils: Issues such as students' overall academic achievement, the distance they have covered in learning, their status compared to the national averages in mathematics and language lessons, and the development of disadvantaged students are discussed in this section. An example statement on this subject is as follows (UK6):

"Students have made good progress in most subjects, including English and mathematics. A combination of good teaching and a highly targeted intervention has been prepared to support students identified as at risk of decline. As a result, students are typically above the national average at the end of the 6th Grade. Generally, students who graduate from this school exceed the national averages in reading, writing and mathematics. Effective support is provided to students with disabilities and those with special education needs by well-trained teachers and teaching assistants. Education and training are well planned to meet student needs. This enabled the students to achieve the progress expected of them."

e) The evaluation of the previous years: This section only contains judgments regarding the personal and pedagogical development of students. It includes a comparison of what the situation was in the previous years and what the current situation is. Also, judgments about whether the students are ready for the next year are also included in this section. An example statement on this subject is as follows (UK4):

"The children are highly aware of the needs of others, they study and play in harmony with each other. They quickly learn to negotiate with each other, resolving disputes without the intervention of adults. The adults provide a safe environment where children learn to assess and manage risk for themselves. Children who stumble or fall during games get up quickly and continue unhurriedly. As a result of superior leadership and teaching, children are provided with the knowledge and skills they need to start the 1st Grade."

Cover (school details): This includes a comprehensive table for each inspected school report. In this table, "Unique reference number, local authority to which it is affiliated, inspection number, school type, school category, the age range of pupils, the gender of pupils, number of students in the school roll, number on roll in the sixth form, the proprietor (founder) (if a private institution), chairman, headteacher, annual fees (if a private institution), telephone number, website, e-mail address, the date of previous school inspection.

Complaints and concerns: An important section is included in some OFSTED reports concerning complaints against the inspectors or the report (UK3). According to the descriptions in this section, if there are complaints about the inspection or the report, these complaints can be filed following the procedures outlined in the 'Make a Complaint About Ofsted' guide on Ofsted's website at www.Ofsted.gov.uk. An example statement on the subject is given below (UK3):

"Any complaints about the inspection or the report should be made following the procedures set out in the guidance 'Complaining about inspections,' which is available from Ofsted's website: www.ofsted.gov.uk."

4. Discussion, Conclusion, and Suggestions

Inspection is a function of the management. It is very difficult to determine the extent to which an uninspected organization has achieved its goals. The effectiveness of the organizations is increased and the institution is improved via inspections. Inspections should be carried out by experts. These experts should record everything they find for the future of the institution. These records constitute the inspection reports. A bureaucratic state is a state where everything is kept under record. This is the reason why inspection reports are of critical importance. The fact that findings in the inspection reports are recorded by experts and inspectors is also important.

During the inspection process, employees know that their performance is being observed and recorded. As a matter of fact, things such as fees can be determined based on performance in some countries and some institutions. Furthermore, inspection reports are not only tools for improvement and performance for employees. but also a source of motivation. In this respect, they have serious effects on the psychology of the employees. Therefore, inspectors must prepare inspection reports carefully.

Inspection reports can be compared to taking an MRI of an organization. It is possible to learn from the inspection reports what is happening in the institution, the stakeholders' views on the school administration, and what the school has managed to achieve in terms of academic achievement. Inspection reports are a feedback tool. Therefore, inspection reports should be prepared very carefully. This study has examined the inspection reports of Turkey and the United Kingdom, two countries with robust inspection systems. Issues worthy of notice identified during the examination of these reports are as follows:

Education inspectors in Turkey are governed by a body headed by the Ministry of National Education. Although education inspection has a deep history in Turkey, the inspection system has not yet managed to achieve the desired quality levels. Education inspectors are employees of the Ministry of National Education. And they supervise institutions or schools affiliated with their Ministry. The reports prepared after the inspections performed by the Education Inspectors of the Ministry of National Education of Turkey are not accessible to the parents and the public. They are not published anywhere. Inspectors send their inspection reports to schools in accordance with the confidentiality principle. This is because privacy is essential ("The principle of confidentiality should be observed in the preparation, presentation and storage of reports" MEB Inspection Guide). After being read by the school administrations, they are filed and the necessary actions are taken.

All inspection reports produced in Turkey are similar. It is possible to say that the centralized structure of the Turkish inspection system is effective in the occurrence of this situation (Demirkasimoglu, 2011, 46). Because it is difficult to expect an original and creative approach from an inspection activity managed by an inspection organization in Ankara that has a total number of 500 employees.

Only certain demographic data, such as the number of teachers, the number of students, etc., differ by school. The inspection reports prepared in Turkey contain a great number of spelling and formatting errors. School-specific findings generally include vague statements. The achievement levels of the schools are not compared with other schools or international exams. The names of the inspectors conducting the inspection are included in the reports.

Parent-teacher association record books are examined during the inspection, but no interviews are made with members of the parent-teacher association. There is no participation in the inspection process. Stakeholder views are not reflected in the report. For example, students are not interviewed in any way and student views about the school are not included in the report. Yavuz and Gulmez (2016) express that the inspection reports should be open to all stakeholders of the school and the opinions of parents and students should be sought in their preparation.

The reports include a detailed review of school documents (books and files to be kept). This shows that, in Turkey, school inspections are rather perceived as the inspection performed for the bureaucratic structure. According to Demirkasimoglu (2011), the mandate of the inspectors should be focused on increasing the quality through inspection and educational guidance. Again, according to Yavuz and Gulmez (2016), it would be more beneficial the place the focus regarding inspection reports on improving education and training rather than checking documents and these reports should be revised to emphasize this. Examination of inspection reports prepared in Turkey reveals that the findings and suggestions towards directly improving the quality of education are very weak. According to Dursun and Altinisik (2019), the reason for this is the inspection organization in the Ministry. Because in the organization responsible for inspection, the matters of guidance and investigation are almost completely intertwined. Because of this situation, inspectors cannot be as useful as they should. Inspection staff needs to focus on issues such as improving, developing, increasing the quality of education and educational consultancy.

The inspection reports do not contain any contact information about the inspectors. OFSTED of the UK is directly affiliated to the Queen. All education inspectors are referred to as Her Majesty's Inspectors. As inspectors who are affiliated to the Queen, they inspect schools and institutions affiliated with the British Ministry of Education. However, OFSTED inspectors are not limited to inspecting schools. For example, babysitters are also supervised by OFSTED. If schools have a religious characteristic, these religious features can be clearly expressed in the OFSTED reports. All inspection reports can be accessed on OFSTED's website. Inspection reports are available to parents and to the public. Inspectors meet with members of the parent-teacher association and parents during the inspection and include their opinions in their reports. Moreover, parents can provide opinions about their school and school management at any time by answering a 14-question questionnaire that is available on the OFSTED website. However, there are also questionnaires for the teachers. Opinions of teachers are received through these questionnaires and these opinions are included in the reports. School documents are reviewed and opinions on them are added to inspection reports. In-class observations are carried out. The names of the inspectors are written on the reports. The inspection reports include OFSTED's telephone and other contact information. Certain inspection reports contain information on what procedures should be applied in case of complaints about the inspectors.

Since the inspection reports include the progress and quality of the education process, it attracts the attention of many groups, especially parents. However, the transparency of inspection reports is related to managerial accountability. It is possible to say that OFSTED reports are successful in this respect. It is seen again that inspection reports contribute to school development (Guzel, Arslan & Aktekin, 2020). Additionally, it is noted grammatical mistakes and vagueness are also problems encountered in the OFSTED reports and there are criticisms that readers have trouble understanding these reports. For example, although the OFSTED reports are texts that are taken into consideration by parents to a great extent, there are criticisms that the language used in these reports is not understood by many parents (Field, Greensteet, Kusel & Parsons, 1996). Likewise, there are studies showing that OFSTED reports cause stress on many directors and that the benefits of these inspections are limited when prior preparations and expenses are included in the calculations (Cuckle, Hodgson & Broadhead, 1998). Moreover, the negativities expressed in regards to these reports also include extremely traumatic results on the occupational lives of the teachers (Case, Case & Catling, 2000).

In conclusion, there are similarities and differences between OFSTED reports and inspection reports in Turkey. There are important similarities in the reports regarding the bureaucratic structure of the schools and the matters subject to inspection, and there are serious differences in terms of the quality of education, participation, and transparency. Inspection reports prepared in Turkey should be made public. Inspection reports should evaluate the students who are being educated in the school that is being inspected and include comparisons with local, national

and international examinations. Opinions of administrators, teachers, students, parents and other stakeholders should be included in the report to make the process more participatory. The language employed in the writing of these reports should be revised.

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